

Psychological Affect of e-Sports in e-Marketing via Computational Methods

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Abstract

E-sports have become a global phenomenon. Recent reports have valued the industry at more than \$612 million, with reach extending from Europe and North America, and to the developing markets of Asia. Nowadays e-Sports is highlighted as an incredibly powerful marketing opportunity for brands. For most enterprises, e-sports is huge, growing, and an attractive marketing opportunity. This isn't new news, but for most brands, gaming is relatively uncharted territory. In the current study, there was an attempt to investigate the profile of e-sports players in order to provide privilege in marketing to promote its brands in a more effective way.

For the data collection, three self-report questionnaires were administered: a) Profile of Mood States [POMS], evaluating the person's mood, positive and negative, and more specifically the tension, anger, sadness, fatigue, confusion and vitality, b) Eysenck Personality Questionnaire, measuring personality traits, c) Emotional Intelligence Questionnaire [TEIQue] clarifying four factors of emotional state; well-being, self-control, emotionality and sociability and d) Brand Personality Appeal [BPA], evaluating three dimensions (favorability, originality, clarity) that are emerged and are empirically demonstrated to directly and positively impact consumer purchase intentions. There were being created their electronic versions through Google Forms service and posted through the website "<http://www.cicos.gr/iccmi2017/paem>". Then the collected data were selected for analysis, with relevant transformations in order to have a suitable form for the implementation of the respective machine learning algorithms included in the software package R.

The results of the present study show among others that mood state, emotional intelligence brand personality can serve as crucial variables and can be prevalent in the marketing literature covering a wide range of topics, including evidence that profile of mood state emotional intelligence and brand personality of the e-sports players can highlight marketing habits and may promote effectively publicity politics.

Keywords: *e-Sports, Profile of Mood States, Emotional Intelligence, Brand Personality, R, Computational Methods*

1. INTRODUCTION

E-Sports is not a new technology or a new frenzy. It is a complete shift in entertainment and culture in the field of digital information systems, with a geometrically increasing amount of time and attention in the first instance to young adults and secondly to the rest of the population. Especially e-Sports are a set of competing video games that are streamed live on the Internet to the public. While live events and tournaments have long been a part of the video game culture, broadband live streaming has now radically expanded the audience that is actively involved or not.

A global community of more than 148 million enthusiastic people, experiencing double growth over the last decade, is now the so-called e-Sports community and yes they can take pride in this. Players can earn seven-figure wages and are sure to be celebrated as rock stars. Tournaments are played in sold-out arenas with tens of thousands of fans. In recent years, one can attend college even with a scholarship in e-Sports. Large companies in the field of Marketing and with big brand names strive with an appropriate approach to e-Sports to participate actively, to influence and to derive value from these new game ecosystems. In the present research we are trying to answer these challenges and show among others that mood state (POMS), personality dimensions (EPQ), emotional intelligence (TEIQue) and brand personality (BPA) of the e-sports players can affect as crucial variables and can be prevalent in the marketing literature covering a wide range of topics, including highlight marketing habits.

1.1. Profile of Mood States (POMS)

Mood refers to a positive or negative emotional state of varying intensity that varies according to the perception of the individual about the circumstances of everyday life. Based on the literature, two basic dimensions have been discovered through the analysis of the main components of multiple mood reports, which reflect four broad moods: positive high activation (enthusiastic, excited, joyful), positive low activation (calm, relaxed, peaceful) High activation (worrying, hostile, twisted) and negative low activation (sad, depressed, disappointed) as shown in Image 1.

Image 12: A model of mood reflecting differences in valence (positivity / negativity) and activation (high energy / low energy)

The Profile of Mood States (POMS) scale was created to evaluate that person's mood. This is a self-referral questionnaire of 65 proposals, which aims at assessing the positive and negative person's mood, and more specifically, the intensity, anger, sadness, fatigue, confusion and vitality. Each sentence includes an adjective, such as nervous, angry, etc. Respondents answer, according to a scale of five grades, whether each adjective responds to how they feel in the last week. There is an abridged form of the questionnaire with 30 questions.

1.2. Eysenck Personality Questionnaire (EPQ)

The personality dimensions introduced by Eysenck are separate types of people, each of which involves a set of features traced back to their habits and their specific reactions. In particular, what is proposed is the detection of specific reactions of the individual, which will give evidence of his usual reactions and hence of his usual behavior. This will allow conclusions to be drawn for some key features of his personality. These attributes are considered as the factors that make up each of the three dimensions of personality (types). The relationship between the reactions and their regular appearance makes them reliable criteria for rendering certain characteristics to the personality of the person.

The diagram proposed by Eysenck in 1947 distinguished the two basic dimensions of the personality, represented

Image 13

by two intersecting axes. At the two poles of the vertical axis, the maximum and minimum values of the dimension that Eysenck called "Emotionality or Instability or Neuroticism" were placed. The maximum value represented the existence of characteristics of instability, neuroticism, while the minimum referred to the existence of characteristics of emotional stability. On the horizontal axis, the other dimension of the personality was placed, the Inwardness - Extraversion. As on the vertical axis, the maximum value was referring to the personality traits of the extroverted type, as opposed to the other pole, that of the minimum value, which set the characteristics of introversion. In detail, the three dimensions of the personality that are proposed have the following characteristics:

Extraversion-introversion [Activity, Sociability, Assertiveness, Expressiveness, Ambition, Dogmatism, and Aggressiveness]: One who is defined as extrovert is social, loves gatherings, has many friends, and does not like reading and studying. Also, has a keen desire for emotion, does not lose opportunities, likes danger, reacts immediately and is generally impulsive. The typical introvert is quiet, isolated, intuitive who prefers books from people, is restrained and stays in a distance, except for very close friends and does not love intense emotions, also treats everyday problems seriously and prefers well-planned life, controls his feelings, is trustworthy, pessimistic and attaches great importance to moral values. Extroverted and introverted differ in their behavior and beliefs.

Neuroticism - Instability - Emotional Stability [Inferiority, Unhappiness, Anxiety, Dependence, Hypochondria, Guilt, and Obsessiveness]: Neuroticism refers to the general emotional instability of the individual, to its emotional hyperactivity and to the tendency to develop neurotic symptoms under stress. People with high neurotic values are anxious, sad, sad, and often sad. When neuroticism is accompanied by high extroversion then the person is irritable, restless, even aggressive. Low prices, on the contrary, refer to an emotionally stable person with mild reactions and a generally stable system of values, attitudes and behavior.

Psychoticism [Risk-taking, Impulsivity, Irresponsibility, Manipulativeness, Sensation-seeking, Tough-mindedness, Practicality]: Further exploration of Eysenck's personality dimensions has led to the observation that there is one more personality variable that manifests in the population as a whole - that is, in healthy and divergent - in the form of reaction patterns and is indicative of the possible appearance of psychotic elements. This variable was the third personality dimension, called "Psychoticism" (P) and also refers to subjective personality traits. This predisposition exists to varying degrees in all individuals, and only its very high value may be an indication of some form of psychosis. The result of these observations was the development of a measurement scale of the three dimensions of the personality (E, N, P) and a complementary dimension of the L, which measures the falsehood of the answers given by the person questioned during the questionnaire. The new scale, presented by the Eysenck couple in 1975, was named the Eysenck Personality Questionnaire (E.P.Q.).

1.3. Trait Emotional Intelligence (TEIQue)

The Trait Emotional Intelligence Questionnaire (TEIQue) is a self-report questionnaire that has been developed to cover the trait EI sampling domain comprehensively. Questionnaire measures of EI have been proliferating over the past few years, and it is important to mention three advantages of the TEIQue over them to justify the focus of this research. First, the TEIQue is based on a psychological theory that integrates the construct into mainstream models of differential psychology. Second, the TEIQue provides comprehensive coverage of the 15 facets of the trait EI sampling domain. Several independent studies have demonstrated the ability of the TEIQue to predict criteria (outcomes) significantly better than other questionnaires. Third, the full TEIQue has excellent psychometric properties. Finally, the TEIQue has been used in numerous studies wherein the assessment of affective aspects of personality was required. These include research in the areas of neuroscience, relationship satisfaction, psychopathology, addictions, reaction time, general

Image 14

health, and behavioral genetics. The TEIQue provides an operationalization for the model of Petrides and colleagues that conceptualizes EI in terms of personality. The test encompasses 15 subscales organized under four factors: well-being, self-control, emotionality and sociability.

The TEIQue is based on Dr. Petrides' trait emotional intelligence theory, which views the construct as a constellation of emotional self-perceptions located at the lower levels of personality hierarchies. Trait EI provides a comprehensive operationalization of the affective aspects of personality. Essentially, it concerns people's beliefs about their emotional abilities (how good we believe we are in identifying, understanding, and managing our own and other people's emotions). These beliefs are very strong predictors of an extraordinarily wide range of behaviors and achievements, many of which are absolutely vital in the workplace (job satisfaction, job stress, leadership, teamwork, organizational citizenship, organizational commitment, etc.).

Well being: The Well-being factor comprises three different traits: Happiness, Optimism and Self-esteem. They measure how people judge their general level of life satisfaction.

Self control: The Self-control factor describes how far people think they can control their impulses or are controlled by them. It comprises three different traits: Impulse Control, Stress Management and Emotional Regulation.

Emotionality: The Emotionality factor comprises four different traits: Empathy, Emotion Perception, Emotion Expression and Relationships. Together they indicate how aware you may be of your own emotions and feelings, as well as those of other people. Scores on these traits tend to reflect how highly you value this 'emotional literacy' and when and how you make use of it.

Sociability: The Sociability factor describes how comfortable people feel in different social contexts, from parties and social gatherings to formal business meetings.

1.4. Brand Personality Appeal (BPA)

The personality of a trademark consists of a combination of human features associated with a brand. Consumers use the personality of a brand name as a means of personal identification but also positioning on the product in question, with the result that it often appears as a personality identity with the personality of that trademark. Within a consumer society, a brand is no longer the subject of financial exchange, recognition, and consumers themselves. Consumers use the brand when their personality helps them identify, place, and recognize themselves. Such an adaptation of course also depends on the ability of the mark to make it attractive to consumers. For this reason, the brand personality must be discreet, attractive and recognizable to all consumers. These brand features determine its personality, the ability of a brand to reach consumers by combining the human characteristics associated with it. Many empirical researches on brand-consumer relationships has shown that brand personality allows consumers to express themselves by shaping and enhancing the relationship between brands and consumers. For this reason, consumers tend to build, develop and strengthen their relationship with the brand.

Figure 22 Conceptual Model

The Conceptual Model of Brand Personality Appeal Scale:

- H1: Brand relationship quality has a positive effect on WOM transmission.
- H2: Brand personality appeal has a positive effect on brand relationship quality.
- H3: Brand personality appeal has a positive effect on WOM transmission.
- H4: Attitudes toward advertising have a positive effect on brand personality appeal.
- H5: Attitudes toward advertising have a positive effect on brand relationship quality.
- H6: Attitudes toward public relations have a positive effect on brand personality appeal.

- H7: Attitudes toward public relations have a positive effect on brand relationship quality.

2. METHODOLOGY

In this paper were applied Computational Methods in order to evaluate and associate the Profile of Mood States (POMS), Brand Personality Appeal (BPA) with Personality Dimensions (EPQ) and Emotional Intelligence (TEIQue) of e-Sports Players. The methodology, that was adopted, consists of three concrete phases. During the first phase electronic questionnaires were created and posted through the website <http://www.cicos.gr>. Subsequently, data were collected and preprocessed from the questionnaires. The data set for analysis was consisted of demographics elements of responders, such as the gender, the birth-place, the place of present residence, educational background of both the respondents and their parents, professional occupation of parents and also of subscales of the POMS, BPA, EPQ and TEIQue tests. During the third phase, the data set was analyzed based on Data Mining techniques and evaluate the results. More specifically, we utilized classification algorithms so as to manage to describe the hidden patterns underlying in the data. Decision trees are a powerful way in order to represent and facilitate statements analysis (psychological) principally, comprising successive decisions and variable results in a designated period.

2.1. Brand Names and Psychological Affect in e-Sports Players

In order to better understand the psychological profile of e-sport players, it is important to investigate interests and activities of players. This element will offer opportunities to brands trademark companies and sponsors to connect with e-Sports users and better address their needs for gaming. Identifying the most effective approach of a company of a known or non-branded brand to e-Sports users and consumers starts with the full understanding of the e-Sports consumer for the optimal marketing effectiveness of the particular company, whether psychological or otherwise. The knowledge of e-sports users' activities, its demographics, its psychological profile and how it is combined with its personality as well as the way it recognizes a brand name and how loyal it is in general in brand names is essential for on line gaming industry to support and reclaim in strategic manner the contact points of the brand with the e-sport consumer. For example, e-sport users like partners or sponsors to e-Sports, trademark companies. According to current research, e-sport users' favorite brand names in total, 5 of the top 10 brands were sporting brands. Only about a year or two ago the e-sports scene was relatively unknown, but big name brands like Coca-cola, Monster, and RedBull became early parts of the e-sports scene, and they have all benefited from this early support.

Recently bigger consumer brands have begun looking into the space such as Comcast, Hewlett Packard, and SAP. In May 2015 a SuperData brief found that the global e-sports market is worth \$612 million dollars with a viewership of 134 million, a number that only continues to increase. The 2013 League of Legends final sold out the Los Angeles Staples Center and in 2014 the League of Legends world championship, broadcast on ESPN, had a concurrent viewership of 27 million.

2.2. Psychological Profile, Personality, Emotional Intelligence in e-Sports Players

Nowadays, more and more people are becoming avid gamers. Gaming culture is quickly becoming a large and going topic. With younger generations of people spending on average around 20 to 40 hours a week playing video games, it's hard to ignore that gaming is receiving a lot of attention. Many questions arise, what is it about video games that are so alluring? Can video games help train minds to specialize in the work force? Are video games even healthy? Each question revolves back to how the gamer reacts to playing video games. The real question is how do video games affect the player psychologically?

Video games have often been associated with negative condensations. Such negative gaming affects theories such as including notion social detachment. Social detachment can be described as the disengagement from participation in a range of societal activities. Two common detachments associated with video games are heightened aggression, and social separation. Heightened aggression is thought to be a critical long term effect of playing violent video games. Heightened aggression as a player has been thought to be the cause of school shootings, lack of sympathy, and other negative highly aggressed connections. Social separation in video games in terminology is when the gamer becomes detached from social and social interactions and loses social skills due to the lack of interactions with live people. Some researchers state that it's not the violence in the video game that causes heightened aggression but each player is different with a separate and varying set of characteristics and it is how the game interacts with each individual's characteristics that determine the amount of long term aggression to be claimed. There is some speculation that video games can cause social detachment through people and real life encounters. Though people don't realize that it's not said game that detaches the

player, it is that said gamer carries the type of personality that play. It is the player that chooses to play the game that already feels socially disconnected without a direct effect of playing video games. Although it seems that a higher number of people who play video games have social impairment, it is not directly connected to video games. Video games have evolved, and now allow us to socialize with people in games such as Halo, Call of duty, World of Warcraft, and so many other games that encourage online multiplayer or co-op multiplayer. Video games as such are now the center of many parties, clubs, and there is even a new aspect on gaming which includes competitive gaming such as e-sports.

Some previous studies have suggested that individual psychological characteristics (including personality traits) may predispose certain individuals to overuse the Internet, and past research has chiefly examined the effects of shyness, anxiety, loneliness, depression, and self-consciousness on the level of Internet use so far. Some other studies reported that Internet addiction to video games seems to be associated with impulsivity, neuroticism, psychoticism, and lie subscale of Eysenck personality questionnaire. Another research examined the relationship between a number of personality traits (sensation seeking, self-control, aggression, neuroticism, state anxiety, and trait anxiety) and online gaming addiction. Five traits (neuroticism, sensation seeking, trait anxiety, state anxiety, and aggression) displayed significant associations with online gaming addiction. The study suggested that those certain personality traits may be important in the acquisition, development, and maintenance of online gaming addiction, although further research is needed to replicate the findings

However, little has been researched about the characteristics linked to “at-risk” populations with such a dependence upon “online games,” especially of aggressive nature, which is one of the important subcategories of Internet addiction. Therefore, to explore the relationship between online e-sports gaming, psychological mood as measured by Profile of Mood States (POMS), psychological characteristics as measured by Eysenck Personality Inventory (EPQ) and emotional intelligence as measured by Trait Emotional Intelligence Questionnaire (TEIQue). Each of these parameters is expected to affect or be affected by one’s gaming activities.

2.2. Data Mining Techniques

Data Mining is an emerging knowledge discovery process of extracting previously unknown, actionable information from very large scientific and commercial databases. It is imposed by the explosive growth of such databases. Usually, a data mining process extracts rules by processing high dimensional categorical and/or numerical data. Classification, clustering and association are the most well known data mining tasks. Classification is one of the most popular data mining tasks. Classification aims at extracting knowledge which can be used to classify data into predefined classes, described by a set of attributes. The extracted knowledge can be represented using various schemas. Decision trees, "if-then" rules and neural networks are the most popular such schemas. A lot of algorithms have been proposed in the literature for extracting classification rules from large relational databases, such as symbolic learning algorithms including decision trees algorithms (e.g. C4.5) and rule based algorithms (e.g. CN2), connectionist learning algorithms (e.g. back{propagation networks), instance-based algorithms (e.g. PEBLS) and hybrid algorithms. Association rules can be used to represent frequent patterns in data, in the form of dependencies among concepts attributes. In this paper, we consider the special case, that is known as the market basket problem, where concepts-attributes represent products and the initial database is a set of customer purchases (transactions).

3. RESULTS

3.1. General Statistics

We asked gamers to rank the most common activities they do while they are not playing or watching e-Sports. The following chart shows how the activities ranked:

Figure 23

3.2. Mining Association Rules

Association Rule Mining is a common technique used to find associations between many variables. In Data Mining, Apriori is a classic algorithm for learning association rules. Apriori is designed to operate on databases containing

transactions (for example data collected from surveys in this case). As is common in association rule mining, given a set of item sets, the algorithm attempts to find subsets which are common to at least a minimum number C of the itemsets.

Apriori uses a "bottom up" approach, where frequent subsets are extended one item at a time, and groups of candidates are tested against the data. The algorithm terminates when no further successful extensions are found. Apriori uses breadth-first search and a tree structure to count candidate item sets efficiently. It generates candidate item sets of length k from item sets of length k - 1. Then it prunes the candidates which have an infrequent sub pattern. According to the downward closure lemma, the candidate set contains all frequent k-length item sets. After that, it scans the transaction database to determine frequent item sets among the candidates.

Association rules present association or correlation between item sets. An association rule has the form of A → B, where A and B are two disjoint item sets.

The Goal: studies whether the occurrence of one feature is related to the occurrence of others.

Three most widely used measures for selecting interesting rules are:

- ✓ **Support** is the percentage of cases in the data that contains both A and B,
- ✓ **Confidence** is the percentage of cases containing A that also contain B, and
- ✓ **Lift** is the ratio of confidence to the percentage of cases containing B.

3.3. Apriori rules visualization

Figure 24

- **Grouped Matrix plot**

Antecedents (columns) in the matrix are grouped using clustering. Groups are represented as balloons in the matrix.

- **Graph**

Represents the rules (or itemsets) as a graph. Specifically of our use, the parameters that were altered are:

- control=list(type="item ms")

Figure 25

- **Paracoord**

Parallel coordinate charts are a visualization that consists of N amount of vertical axes,

Figure 26

each representing a unique data set of 61 rules, with lines drawn across the axes. The lines show the relationship between the axes, much like scatter plots, and the patterns that the lines form indicates the relationship. We can also gather details about the relationships between the axes when you see the clustering of lines. Let's take a look at this using the chart below as an example. Specifically of our use, the parameters that were altered are:

➤ control=list(reorder=TRUE)

Apriori rules

For the top 117 rules that were extracted from the apriori the following parameters were altered:

- support: A numeric value for the minimal support of an item set
- confidence: A numeric value for the minimal confidence of rules/association hyperedges

Specifically of our use: Support: 50%, Confidence: 90%

The top 6 rules

{EI_sociability=LOW, POMS_distress=LOW}	{POMS_depression=LOW}	0.6041667	1.0000000
{EPQ_E_Extraversion.Introversion=HIGH}	{POMS_Tension_Anxiety=LOW}	0.6250000	0.9677419
{Do.ypu.buy..sportsweat.to.have.athletic.appearance.during.your.game.=NO, POMS_anger_hostility=LOW}	{POMS_Tension_Anxiety=LOW}	0.6041667	0.9354839
EI_emotionality=LOW, POMS_distress=LOW}	{POMS_anger_hostility=LOW}	0.6041667	1.0000000
{EI_well_being=LOW, POMS_Tension_Anxiety=LOW}	{EI_emotionality=LOW}	0.5208333	0.9259259
{EI_well_being=LOW, POMS_Tension_Anxiety=LOW, POMS_anger_hostility=LOW}	{EI_emotionality=LOW}	0.5208333	0.9615385

Table 6

3.4. Correlation Analysis

Figure 27

Correlation is any of a broad class of statistical relationships involving dependence, though in common usage it most often refers to the extent to which two variables have a linear relationship with each other.

As it is shown above, there is high negative correlation between EI and POMS questionnaires and some low positive correlation between EI and the emotion factor of the BPA questionnaire.

If the measures of correlation used are product-moment coefficients, the correlation matrix is the same as the covariance matrix of the standardized random variables $X_i / \sigma(X_i)$ for $i = 1, \dots, n$.

3.5. K-means Clustering Analysis

K-means clustering is a method of vector quantization, originally from signal processing, that is popular for cluster analysis in data mining. k-means clustering aims to partition n observations into k clusters in which each observation belongs to the cluster with the nearest mean, serving as a prototype of the cluster.

Figure 28

For each cluster iteration, the cluster centers are multiplied by the first loading of the principal components of the original data. Thus offering a weighted mean of the each cluster center dimensions that might give a decent representation of that cluster (this method has the known limitations of using the first component of a PCA for dimensionality reduction)

The second split is a good one (in the manner that it splits the first cluster into two clusters which are not “close” to each other).

4. CONCLUSION

Concluding, mood state, emotional intelligence brand personality can serve as crucial variables and can be prevalent in the marketing literature covering a wide range of topics; including evidence that profile of mood state emotional intelligence and brand personality of the e-sports players can highlight marketing habits and may promote effectively publicity politics.

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